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The Greek COPSOQ v.3 Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece.

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Introduction and Aims

We aim:

- I. To provide the Greek validated version based on the German version of COPSOQ V.3
- II. To develop and validate introduce an *agile Organizational Change Assessment Framework (OCAF)*, based on the current research findings and conclusions.

Methods

The study is a longitudinal (follow-up) study (N=1000). We use the Greek COPSOQ v.3 dimensions as Organizational Change Context and Organizational Change Impact variables. Due to a variety of corresponding management of change related studies [[Oreg (2013), Smollan(2017), De Jong (2016), Van der Voet(2017), Holten (2016), Kuipers (2014)] and corresponding COPSOQ studies the above approach can be considered as important from a both "*theoretical*" and "*practical implications*" perspectives.

Results

The linguistic validation process, assessment of reliability, construct validity and the content validity of the Greek COPSOQ v.3 in collaboration with the International COPSOQ Network and F.F.A.W². The study also includes the investigation of the direct and indirect impact of emergent organizational on human capital documented with an in-depth analysis of the psychosocial cause & effect mechanisms that explain these effects.

Conclusions and/or implications

In the existing management of planned or emergent organizational change literature, many studies use a high number of variables and factors with either complex or computationally demanding models for assessing organizational change, making standard analyses (like longitudinal invariance) difficult, time consuming or not applicable at all. This study faces that deficiency, by utilizing linear, non-linear and machine learning algorithms (AI) in psychosocial-risk data analysis.

** For the COPSOQ session*

*** The research team confirms, that the above abstract can be published*